

BRILL

BIJDRAGEN TOT DE TAAL-, LAND- EN
VOLKENKUNDE 181 (2025) 159–190

brill.com/bki

Young, Modern, and *Tjabul*

Problematizing Obscenity in 1950s Indonesia

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Received 7 October 2024 | Accepted 17 August 2025 |
Published online 25 September 2025

Abstract

This article examines the cultural politics of obscenity (*tjabul*) in 1950s' Indonesia, a decade marked by ideological flux, technological transformation, and contested visions of modernity. Drawing on archival materials from periodicals such as *Star Weekly*, *Wanita*, and *Harian Rakjat*, it explores how obscenity was defined, debated, and regulated across literary, visual, and political domains. Through interconnected case studies within literary and popular scenes, the article reveals how affective expressions were used to police bodies, regulate media, and shape national identity. Engaging with Sara Ahmed's theory of the politics of emotions, it argues that *tjabul* was not a fixed category but rather a performative discourse shaped by colonial legacies, gendered anxieties, and postcolonial aspirations. The article situates obscenity within broader debates on artistic freedom, women's visibility, and cultural sovereignty, showing how the media became both a moral compass and a battlefield of beliefs in a nation still defining itself.

Keywords

1950s Indonesia – postcolonial – obscenity – social commentary

In 1954, provocative photographs of an Indonesian movie star, Numaningsih, posing naked were circulated on the black market in Jakarta and Medan, causing a national scandal. The visual content of the photographs remains unclear;

Published with license by Koninklijke Brill BV | DOI:10.1163/22134379-bja10069

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contemporary media described them merely as ‘nude photographs’ (*gambar telanjang*) without offering further detail. The images were never published publicly, and neither the photographer’s identity nor that of the distributors was disclosed. Nurnaningsih, however, remained highly visible throughout the scandal, frequently appearing both in news coverage and during police inquiries. Summoned by authorities, she stated that she was unaware of the photographs’ circulation. While she acknowledged consenting to pose, she firmly denied giving permission for their distribution.¹ Nurnaningsih asserted that her decision to pose nude was to challenge and transform the prevailing ‘conservative attitudes’ (*pandangan jang KOLOT*) towards art.² In a letter to her family in Magelang, she explained her motive as her golden ticket to Hollywood. Her father reacted differently to this issue by calling her ‘my naughty daughter’ (*anak saja jang nakal*) who had disgraced her family’s name. Meanwhile, one of her sisters, who was a member of a left-wing women’s organization, the Gerakan Wanita Indonesia or Gerwani (Indonesian Women’s Movement) called for the eradication of all obscene pictures and materials that promoted Western immorality.³ The scandal surrounding these photographs of Nurnaningsih illustrates the tensions surrounding morality in the early decades of independent Indonesia. Her case encapsulated the early post-independence anxieties surrounding public visibility, sexual autonomy, and Western influence, all filtered through the lens of the term *tjabul*⁴ (obscene).

1 I drew much of the information regarding Nurnaningsih’s case from a news compilation published by the Medan-based press PB Duaempatlima, titled *Nurnaningsih affair*. This volume not only documents the scandal’s media coverage but also includes interviews with Nurnaningsih and prominent figures within the film industry, alongside editorial commentary and opinion pieces. The publisher had previously released a comparable work addressing President Sukarno’s controversial fourth marriage, titled *Seputar perkawinan Sukarno Hartini* (On the marriage of Sukarno and Hartini) (Djambak n.y.)

2 ‘Obrolan Mang Ganda’, *Suara Merdeka*, 15-10-1954.

3 ‘Nurnaningsih jang telanjang didengar keterangannya oleh polisi Djakarta’, *Suara Merdeka*, 6-10-1954; ‘Peristiwa Nurnaningsih: Menimbulkan kesedihan dikalangan keluarganya’, *Kedaulatan Rakjat*, 29-10-1954.

4 The word *tjabul* (today spelled *cabul* in Indonesian) collocates with *asusila* (indecent), *tidak sopan* (impolite), and *kotor* (dirty). *Tjabul* is an adjective, so it is usually part of a modifier, but it may also be used as a noun, connoting ‘obscenity’. In the second edition of the *Kamus umum bahasa Indonesia* (Indonesian general dictionary; 1954), the entry *tjabul* means ‘vile and dirty (behaviours); inappropriate’, and the example is attached to the nouns ‘books (pictures)’ and ‘women’. The derivatives include *bertjabul* (verb), which is close in meaning to ‘spreading in the manner of an epidemic’; *mentjabul(i)* (verb), which may mean to sexually harass (women) or to violate (sovereignty); and *pertjabulan* (noun), which means an obscene case/affair/matter (Poerwadarminta 1954:837). The words *porno* (pornographic) and *porno-grafi* (pornography), however, had yet to be popular or used in the media, and the dictionary

In 1950s Indonesia, the term *tjabul* emerged as a powerful site of cultural anxiety and ideological contestation. Throughout the decade, obscenity became part of literary criticism and media commentary, as editors, publishers, and cultural critics grappled with foreign influences and the moral boundaries of creative expressions. Far from being a fixed legal category, *tjabul* was emotionally charged and ideologically fluid, invoked to regulate bodies, criticize foreign influence, and define the moral boundaries of a newly independent nation. Whether in newspapers, magazines, political speeches, or cultural meetings, obscenity was not simply seen; it was also felt. Those feelings carried political weight.

This article explores how *tjabul* functioned as a contested discourse shaped by affective responses and ideological agendas. By exploring several cases, Sara Ahmed draws out a theory of affective economies. In the postcolonial Indonesian context, I argue that emotional expressions surrounding *tjabul* reflected the notions that it was a threat to social order and national pride, and to the country's imagined futures. Obscenity, in the following cases, was not a neutral descriptor; it was a performative tool used to construct national identity and enforce moral conformity.

Media outlets played an important role in shaping the discourse of *tjabul*. Magazines and newspapers did not merely reflect public sentiment but also actively produced it, channelling affect to construct narratives about modernity, morality, and cultural values. Through editorials, advice columns, and readers' letters, they offered various visions of Indonesian identity by defining what was to be embraced and what was to be excluded. This article examines interrelated cases that illuminate the emotional and ideological life of *tjabul*: the mainstream literary scene responding to the circulation of *batjaan tjabul* (obscene reading materials); visual technologies enhancing obscenity, including the scandal surrounding the nude photographs of Numaningsih; and politicians and the public reacting to moral decline linked to the nation-building project. These cases illustrate how obscenity was defined through emotional responses and political positioning, often targeting women's visibility and Western influence.

The source materials used for this article include editorial commentary, cultural reporting, and personal letters published in Indonesian periodicals in the 1950s. These texts offer insight into how obscenity was constructed and contested in everyday discourse. Crucially, the difficulty of identifying

at that time did not record these words. They later became popular and, in the 1960s, replaced *tjabul* in the media (Rachim 1977). In general, *tjabul* can be associated with works of art or entertainment and behaviours that were deemed to be sexually inappropriate.

what counted as *batjaan tjabul* (obscene reading materials), as we shall see in the debates in literary circles, emphasizes the instability of the category and the emotional labour involved in its policing. Rather than treating obscenity as a stable legal concept, this article interrogates its affective and ideological dimensions, revealing how *tjabul* became a lens through which postcolonial Indonesia negotiated its moral compass, cultural identity, and political future.

1 The Roaring Fifties: The Years of Living Obscenely

The decade of the 1950s provides a roaring time for Indonesian historiography. The period, as Adrian Vickers reminds us, should be regarded as a distinct and formative period in Indonesian historiography, which was marked by vibrant political experimentation and cultural contestation that was important in shaping the contours of the national identity (Vickers 2008). Furthermore, Henk Schulte Nordholt highlights the 1950s as dynamic, shaped by a desire for modernity, yet simultaneously constrained by entrenched social structures and bureaucratic stagnation (Schulte Nordholt 2011). The decade is also often subsumed within broader narratives that stretch from the 1945 proclamation of independence to the 1965–1966 regime change. This framing, though useful for tracing continuities, tends to obscure the specificity of the 1950s as a period of openness, flux, and contested visions of nationhood, as Vickers and Schulte Nordholt argue. Thus, it is important to assess the decade on its own terms to avoid viewing it as an interlude.

This article builds on research on Indonesia in that decade that mainly focuses on the history of mainstream political and cultural movements. Scholars have approached 1950s Indonesia as a decade of intense political and cultural negotiation. Kevin W. Fogg analyses how socialism was rhetorically adapted under Sukarno (Fogg 2021), while Farabi Fakhri argues that the Liberal Democracy period (1950–1957), despite formally being democratic, also laid the groundwork for the authoritarian governance of the following regime (Fakhri 2020). In terms of education, Agus Suwignyo links educational reform to postcolonial citizenship (Suwignyo 2017), and Nur Wulan examines the construction of national masculinity in youth-oriented literature to evoke the revolutionary spirit and collective ethos (Wulan 2022). With the rise of women's participation in the public sphere, Saskia E. Wieringa and Elizabeth Martyn foreground women's activism through Gerwani and the Kongres Wanita Indonesia (Kowani, Indonesian Women's Congress), positioning women not only as cultural subjects but also as political agents within the nation's contested modern-

ity (Martyn 2005; Wieringa 2002). Furthermore, John Ingleson (2022) provides a comprehensive account of the role of labour unions in shaping democratic practice and postcolonial identity (Ingleson 2022). These works reveal the 1950s not as a merely transitional phase but as a politically generative period during which diverse ideological and institutional actors actively participated in constructing the national identity.

On the other hand, Indonesia still faced problems as part of the aftermath of the Revolutionary War. In the 1950s, divorce rates surged, particularly in Java, where, as Gavin W. Jones observes, up to one-third of marriages ended in dissolution. He attributes this phenomenon to rapid social change and Islamic legal frameworks that allowed for relatively accessible divorce procedures (Jones 1994). Previously, Daniel S. Lev examined the role of Islamic courts, which enabled straightforward divorce processes while local customs minimized the stigma (Lev 1972). Furthermore, Terence H. Hull, Endang Sulistyaningsih, and Gavin W. Jones argued that the sharp rise in divorce was closely linked to post-war urbanization, which destabilized traditional family structures and pushed newly single, young women, who had often been economically dependent on husbands or parents, into city life. Without social protections and with limited employment options, they found prostitution to be one of the few viable survival strategies (Hull, Sulistyaningsih, and Jones 1997).

Literary writers of the period portrayed the drab realities of everyday life across the social classes, capturing the precarity of the post-war conditions, in which poverty and uncertainty led to corrupted morals. Mochtar Lubis, Pramoedya Ananta Toer, and S. Rukiah, among others, responded to the social fracturing of 1950s Indonesia in their works. Lubis's novel *Jalan tak ada ujung* (*A road with no end*, 1952), portrays moral powerlessness and masculine anxiety through the character Guru Isa, who suffers both mental and erectile dysfunctions after independence. Toer's short story collection *Cerita dari Jakarta* (*Tales from Jakarta*, 1956) lays bare class divisions through vignettes of ordinary Jakartans struggling in a city marked by postcolonial inequality and alienation. Meanwhile, Rukiah, one of the few women writers of the time, through her collection of short stories and poems, *Tandus* (1952), focuses on the gendered experience, showing women's intellectual aspirations and emotional interiority amid social expectations. Through these narratives, the authors expose how class, gender, and morality shaped everyday life in the 1950s.

As reflected in the examples of literary works given above, the declining morale contributed to the destabilization of the concept that was later defined as the ideal family. The late Dutch colonial project of modernization had introduced the concept of the nuclear family—where women held central domestic roles—to elite Javanese society, which later adopted the idea as part of its social

restructuring. Meanwhile, nationalists in the early twentieth century, such as Raden Supomo and Mohammad Hatta, strove, although with their own agenda, to introduce a broader conception of the family (Sugiyama 2007). In postcolonial times, women's participation increased in various aspects of life; their visibility was deemed as progress and, somehow, as a threat to the stability of the nuclear family. Journalist Tan Fay Thjion, for example, criticized this destabilization of the family as a consequence of emancipation, while leftist women activists, such as Suharti, proposed a more equal division of labour, as women activists now had to share their time between their domestic and public roles. Politicians, cultural actors, and the public alike reinterpreted the family as being a foundational site for political education, emphasizing women's role in nurturing civic values that would support the nation-building project (Febriani 2021). These shifts highlight how the family became a contested arena where modernity, nationalism, and gender politics converged. The unravelling of the idealized family structure, incited by rising family separations, shifting gender roles, and urbanization, also paved the way for other social phenomena that were widely framed as moral crises, such as infidelity and prostitution, particularly in public discourse.

2 Visible, Speakable, Contested: The Cultural Politics of Obscenity

The shifting discourses around family and gender also intersected with evolving notions of morality and obscenity, which were deeply informed by colonial legacies and cultural anxiety. In this context, 'obscenity' refers not merely to sexual content but to broader anxieties over what should be visible, speakable, or socially acceptable (Heath 2010; Nead 1992). In Indonesia, the colloquial term *tjabul* often blurred boundaries between pornography and obscenity, signalling transgression of both artistic norms and moral expectations. Western colonial aesthetics, particularly Victorian values, had long established a moral framework that equated visual and verbal frankness about sex with immorality (Sigel 2001), and this logic was embedded in legal and cultural regulation across the empire.

Under European imperialism, obscenity laws served to discipline both metropolitan and colonial bodies, reinforcing racial hierarchies by branding native sexuality as uncivilized (Said 1978). In colonial Indonesia, Dutch authorities viewed Eurasian (*Indo*) girls' perceived sexual openness as a threat to European ideals, leading to efforts to 'rescue' them through education and domestic training (Gouda 1995). Such initiatives were rooted in Orientalist fantasies that simultaneously vilified and romanticized native femininity. These colonial nar-

ratives did not vanish after independence. Instead, they continued to shape postcolonial discourse, whereby questions of morality often collided with visions of progress and modernity (Massad 2007).

In examining the cultural anxiety surrounding *tjabul* in postcolonial Indonesia, Sara Ahmed's framework of emotional politics offers a relevant lens. Ahmed argues that emotions such as shame, disgust, and fear are not merely individual reactions but public performances that shape collective identities (Ahmed 2004). Moral outrage over *tjabul* was often framed as the defence of national virtue while at the same time serving to obscure deeper tensions around gender, media, and modernity. The feeling of disgust, mentioned by Ahmed in the context of the racialized bodies of asylum seekers in the UK, would 'stick' to a *tjabul* object, with these being associated with Western influence and female visibility, and thus marked for regulation. The fear of moral collapse in Indonesia, triggered by the prevalence of erotic media and obscenity, was also weaponized to delineate the boundaries of acceptable citizenship and cultural belonging. As we shall see in the following sections, such affective expressions linked *tjabul* to the construction of the national identity.

The idea of regulating obscenity was prevalent in the 1950s as part of state attempts to counter immoral Western influences. In Singapore in 1956, Malay religious sentiment demanded censorship of what was considered immoral for Malay society (Harper 1999). Similarly, Jennifer Lindsay traces the history of Indonesia's regulations on pornography. However, despite the section focusing on the post-Soeharto moral panic, the different perspectives and historical development, including the absence of the word 'pornography' in the 1950s, highlight the issue's continuity rather than its differences. (Lindsay 2011). Indonesia's regulatory framework dates back to Dutch colonial law, codified in the 1946 Kitab Undang-Undang Hukum Pidana (KUHP, Indonesian Criminal Code). Sections 281 and 282 still preserve the rules governing materials and actions that would 'undermine public decency'.⁵ Section 281 states punishment for 'those who voluntarily and openly violate morality' and Section 282 regu-

5 Years later, in 2006, the Indonesian public was introduced to a new term, *pornoaksi* (pornographic action), which was specifically coined to define actions that exploit sexuality and obscenity in public. This term was inserted in a proposed bill that would regulate the spread of pornography. Inevitably the attempt caused a stir in which religious (Islamic in particular) organizations were in favour of the bill and activists, women's organizations, academics, and artists saw the bill as problematic and discriminatory to marginalized groups. The bill finally became a law (Undang-Undang No. 44 Tahun 2008 tentang Pornografi; Law No. 44 of 2008 on Pornography), and the word *pornoaksi* was later dismissed due to its ambiguity. For an analysis of the 2006 Bill, see Allen 2007; for an analysis of the impact of the law on cultural diversity, see Bellows 2011.

lates the circulation and exhibition of materials ‘whose contents are found to violate morality’ (Barker 2015). These legal, cultural, and historical continuities exemplify how moral regulation has persisted as a tool for shaping public norms and identity.

While legal codes laid the groundwork for state control, the public perception of morality unfolded most vibrantly through popular media. In 1950s Indonesia, mass media and publishing democratized access to entertainment and information, where morality became a vibrant public conversation shaped by everyday readers. Obscenity and moral concern entered daily conversations and popular spaces, reflecting the public’s growing role in shaping cultural norms. Popular publications flourished with increasingly diverse readerships as part of a broader campaign to educate the masses. No longer confined to political messaging, mass media evolved into spaces for entertainment, social commentary, and the negotiation of values. Readers’ letters and ‘agony aunt’ pages became fascinating arenas for inclusive dialogues where voices beyond the intellectual elites could be heard. Often guided by a respected—sometimes anonymous—figure, these exchanges created meaningful conversations that complemented magazine and newspaper articles, capturing the contemporary concerns.

Meanwhile, publishing companies and bookstores thrived by offering more diverse selections of reading materials. Foreign publications, whether original, translated, or locally adapted, introduced new moral and cultural norms that sparked debate across the literary scene and beyond. This development was supported by advancements in technology following the Second World War. Instruments such as photocomposition, chromogenic printing (also known locally as *afdruk*), and xerography enabled faster and more effective large-scale printing. Visuals became more colourful, sounds more captivating, and printed imagery more accessible, allowing mass entertainment to cross the class divides. In this dynamic context, morality and immorality were no longer simply abstract ideals but also part of an evolving cultural landscape shaped by ordinary people’s encounter with modernity.

As mass media expanded and moral discourse entered the public domain, concerns about obscenity spilled into the literary arena. Writers, critics, and publishers found themselves negotiating the boundaries of artistic freedom and moral responsibility, particularly as popular books and adapted materials from foreign literature introduced new sensibilities that often clashed with local values and nationalist ideals. These tensions included institutional and intellectual debates. The following section examines how the mainstream literary scene discussed how literary workers and authorities should respond to the surge in obscene publications (*batjaan tjabul*), foregrounding the political

stakes of defining obscenity and questioning whose morality should govern the limits of expression.

3 Sense and Sensibility: The Literary Scene's Response to *batjaan tjabul*

The literary scene in the 1950s, as in many aspects of life at that time, was highly influenced by the idea of being modern, rooted in colonial legacies. During the early twentieth century, the Dutch government played a controlling role in determining public reading materials in their efforts to 'educate' the natives through Balai Pustaka, the state-run publishing bureau (Fitzpatrick 2000; Jedamski 1992). Rising literacy, particularly in Latin script, inspired the nationalist movements, as education ignited a growing desire for liberation. Having control over publications, the colonial authorities drew a line between 'appropriate' literature that promoted law and order and unregulated publications (*batjaan liar*), often written in so-called vernacular Low Malay (Farid and Razif 2008). Works, particularly by the native press, that refused to conform to the standard and challenged the colonial authority were subject to *persdelict* and *persbreidel* (constant monitoring and censorship), and Draconian laws, whereby journalists, writers, and activists were sent for imprisonment in Boven Digul (Yamamoto 2019).

This paradox, however, prevailed after colonialism. The drive to uphold literary standards continued, as the issue of *batjaan tjabul* threatened the dignity of 'serious' literature. Indonesian literature in the 1950s was indeed serious, in the sense that Indonesian writers found new opportunities, and women authors increasingly gained visibility within the mass media.⁶ Literary congresses and international conferences frequently discussed problems in literary scenes, including the growing number of publications of 'unserious' pulp literature that challenged artistic and moral integrity.

Responding to the widespread publication of *batjaan tjabul*, the Organisasi Pengarang Indonesia (OPI, Indonesian Writers Organization)⁷ organized an

6 Literary critic A. Teeuw only recognizes two women writers from this period, Suwarsih Djopuspito and S. Rukiah, and briefly mentions the poet Siti Nuraini (Teeuw 1986). In the 1950s, Nh. Dini and Titie Said started their authorship writing short stories before becoming known as novelists. With the rise of periodicals, many women writers were engaged in journalism, such as SK Trimurti and Herawati Diah.

7 There is not sufficient information about this organization. The minutes of the meeting were later published in 1957 by Balai Pustaka, indicating the possibility of the former's connection

exclusive meeting in 1956 to address the issue. The event brought together three prominent intellectuals—Sutan Takdir Alisjahbana, Hamka, and Gajus Siagian—as keynote speakers, alongside other attendees invited to share their perspectives on this issue. The meeting aimed to produce a working definition of obscenity and to offer corrective guidance for *pengarang tjabul* (obscene writers) on the path to authorship. The minutes from this meeting were later published in 1957 under the title ‘Apakah batjaan tjabul?’ (What is obscenity in literature?).

Despite their differing political and religious orientations, both Alisjahbana and Hamka acknowledged the difficulty of defining obscenity that transgressed space and time. Alisjahbana viewed obscenity as a symptom of broader cultural shifts, particularly the rise of modernity and the changing roles of women. He suggested that women’s increasing visibility in public spaces, outside their domestic roles, contributed to the emergence of immoral literature. Alisjahbana argued that obscene books were not the root of the problem but part of a larger ‘cultural crisis’, something that Hamka agreed with.

Hamka, on the other hand, warned about the peril of neglecting religion and the tendency for moral decline among the younger generation. As an Islamic scholar and writer, he argued that instead of only focusing on science to support the argument on obscenity, religion might provide a better solution, something that Alisjahbana ignored. Both speakers expressed concern about youth education: Hamka lamented students’ defiance of parental authority and disregard for schooling, while Alisjahbana suggested channelling their ‘raging hormones’ into more positive activities. On whether obscene books directly corrupted young minds, they came to opposing conclusions. Hamka strongly believed that such reading materials contributed to young people’s failure in education while Alisjahbana remained ambivalent, questioning whether obscene literature was a cause or consequence of moral decline.

Another important point discussed in this meeting was how to respond to the proliferation of *pengarang tjabul*. Although no specific names or titles were mentioned, ‘serious’ writers were concerned that their works had to compete with sensationalist literature. Gajus Siagian proposed that the solution lay in providing ‘healthy’ reading materials (*batjaan jang sehat*) and ensuring suffi-

to this institution. The membership included writers whose names were not clearly recorded, except for those whose welcoming speeches were included in the book: Haksan Wirasutisna (novelist and member of the Editorial Board), J.C.T. Simorangkir (academic and politician who served as chief administrator), and Dr Marbangun (who served as chair of the Honour Council). The writer Achdiat Kartamihardja was recorded as having served as the vice chair. The attendees of the meeting were only indicated by their names as they delivered their opinions.

cient compensation for authors, suggesting that economic precarity contributed to the production of obscene books. His use of ‘healthy’ implied a hygienic metaphor for literary decency, though he avoided offering concrete examples of what such literature might look like. Siagian also noted the subjectivity of obscenity, remarking that some people might find tales from the Old Testament racier than contemporary fiction.

The debate continued, with Alisjahbana responding to Hamka and Siagian, while other attendees also contributed their opinions. Although they agreed that obscenity was inherently subjective, they also warned that it was even more dangerous not to act. It is important to highlight that not a single woman’s view was recorded, despite women being present at the meeting. Hasan Akmal, one of the attendees, acknowledged this silence and encouraged the women to participate. But by the end of the discussion, no women had spoken or voiced their views on the issue, and no further encouragement for them to speak was recorded in the meeting.

The meeting concluded with a definition of obscenity based on the discussion, signed by the OPI chairperson, J.C.T. Simorangkir, and its secretary, S. Sastrawinata. The meeting agreed that *batjaan tjabul* is

a writing or picture that may violate the sense of decency; if the writing or picture does not contain the slightest value but only a desire/spirit to intentionally illicit lust, so that according to applicable norms (religion, divinity, science, etc.) in a certain period and a certain society, it creates thoughts that draw people who read/hear/see it into a violation of decency.⁸

HAMKA et al. 1957:91

The phrase ‘may violate the sense of decency’—or, in Alisjahbana’s words, *aanstoot voor de eerbaarheid*—was constantly reiterated, not only at this meeting but also in any attempt to distinguish between literature that incited lust for profit and literature that served educational or cultural purposes. While Alisjahbana argued that texts such as medical books or ancient manuscripts from pre-modern times should be exempt from moral judgement due to their

8 ‘[...] suatu tulisan atau gambar dapat melanggar perasaan kesopanan, djika tulisan atau gambar itu tidak sedikitpun mengandung nilai, melainkan hanja mengandung keinginan/semangat untuk dengan sengadja membangkitkan nafsu berahi belaka, sehingga menurut normaz (agama, ketuhanan, keilmuan, dsb.) jang berlaku dalam sesuatu djaman dan dalam sesuatu masjarakat menimbulkan pikiran-pikiran jang menyeret orang jang membaca/mendengar/melihatnja pada pelanggaran kesusilaan’.

intent, no concrete examples were provided. The distinction between ‘proper’ and ‘obscene’ reading materials remained elusive, as interpretations differed significantly. As with debates on pornography elsewhere, the OPI’s definition echoed the tension between authorial intention and moral regulation (Sigel 2001). The urge to police literature was as much about protecting public morality as it was about safeguarding literary authority.

The urgency of the issue was further underscored by legal proceedings reported in the newspaper *Kedaulatan Rakjat* on 23 August 1956. The case centred on a short story titled ‘Dan akhirnya djatuhlah Aminah’ (And finally Aminah fell) by Jussac MR, published in *Bikini* magazine. It was unclear who brought the case to the court. Although the author was not among the defendants, three individuals were brought to trial under Section 282 (2) of the Criminal Code for distributing obscene materials: Tony Suprpto (the editor-in-chief), R.Fx. Soesilo (the illustrator), and Im. Santoso (a caricaturist). The case illustrated how the court and the defendants attempted to decide if the accused had committed the crime of publishing obscenity. Suprpto initially denied the charge, claiming his editorial choices were influenced by ‘the morally damaged society’ (*terbawa suasana masyarakat jang telah rusak moraalnja*). He also imputed the government’s failure to take decisive action against moral violations. Here, personal editorial decisions were attributed to a larger problem; society and the state showed that this problem needed urgent intervention.

Before the OPI meeting, the prominent Indonesian postcolonial writer Pramoedya Ananta Toer had already intervened in the debate on *tjabul*. In his 1953 essay, published in *Indonesia* magazine, he referred to this problem as ‘*keributan*’, a term that connotes not just a debate or an exchange of views but also noise and disruption. He openly criticized religious groups for their intervention in the personal space and their failure to define obscenity with clarity. Pramoedya called on literary critics to serve as gatekeepers, offering authoritative guidelines for distinguishing *batjaan tjabul*, particularly for educators, and warned of the sacrilege of incompetent, self-proclaimed critics.

For Pramoedya, the desire for obscenity was not a moral flaw but a reflection of reality. To deny its existence was, in his opinion, to lie about reality. He concluded that a book could be considered obscene only if its sole purpose was profit, and that readers should be equipped with the knowledge to distinguish such intent (Toer 1953). Through this critique, Pramoedya framed obscenity as a social mirror; its existence unavoidable and its interpretation inherently political. His call for literary critics to assert their authority foreshadowed the concerns raised in the OPI meeting three years later.

Pramoedya’s critique was not simply a lone voice but part of the wider landscape of ideological conflict and cultural redefinition that came to char-

acterize Indonesian literature in the 1950s. It was a time of confusion and ‘contradiction’, a buzzword that at one point became a source of *keributan*, including in the literary scene. In this way, it echoed the earlier ‘Polemik Kebudayaan’ of the 1930s, or, as Claire Holt put it, ‘The Great Debate’, when Indonesian writers and intellectuals contested competing visions of national identity. The decade witnessed a growing divide between writers and artists aligned with socialist realism and those committed to universal humanism. The Lembaga Kebudayaan Rakyat (Lekra, Institute of People’s Culture) championed ‘people’s culture’, promoting artistic expressions that encouraged social change. Until 1965, Lekra remained a strong force in both domestic and international cultural spaces, gaining massive support from the people (Foulcher 1986).

Amid these tensions, Pramoedya’s view on obscenity seemed to contradict the socialist realist view of pornography. While his 1953 essay criticized moralistic constraints, in 1963 he declared his support for socialist realism as an attempt to reinterpret the Indonesian literary tradition beyond the Balai Pustaka’s canon. In doing so, he also challenged the Gelanggang writers, whose humanist values he viewed as complicit with colonial legacies (Heinschke 1996). Pramoedya’s evolving position exemplifies how literary figures negotiated the concepts of aesthetic freedom and political and social responsibility in the rapidly changing postcolonial setting.

While intellectuals and cultural gatekeepers debated the ethics of literary production, the publishing market responded distinctly, as reflected in the widespread circulation of *batjaan tjabul*, which posed a persistent challenge to postcolonial Indonesian literature. During this period, texts categorized as *batjaan tjabul* were often referred to as *sastra Medan* (Medanese literature), pointing to the name of the city where many of them were published. The mainstream literary scene in Jakarta strongly criticized these works as having ‘shallow emotions, cheap sentiments, and moral irresponsibility’, and argued ‘that they would ultimately poison the mind’ (Plomp 2012:377).

Typically pocket-sized, printed on low-quality paper, and marked by suggestive cover illustrations, these publications signalled a clash between populist appeal and the elite’s definition of literary value. As in many contexts, for example in nineteenth-century and interwar Britain (Sigel 2001), the Indonesian bibliography of erotica was difficult to trace: author and publisher names, along with the publication dates, were modified or excluded to avoid persecution. This anonymity complicates efforts to systematically identify and study the genre. Even assembling the materials by publisher or presumed author is complicated, as most figures remain peripheral in the mainstream literary scene.

Despite its prevalence, Indonesian erotic literature has received little scholarly attention. The lack of acknowledgement of erotic materials in Indonesian literary scholarship and authorship may correlate with the idea that writers should educate their readers. Such a compulsion resulted in authors as well as educators deciding on the appropriate texts for the younger generation. Another possible factor is that the self-consciousness among modern Indonesian writers meant that they sanitized or avoided erotic themes in an attempt to cultivate a rational and modern image (Ahmad 1969; Aveling 1969; Mohamad 1969).

Instead of debating whether certain books contain pornographic materials, it may be more productive to examine how obscenity was framed within the publishing industry. As Alan Hunt suggests, this approach reveals the 'social imaginary of sexuality', the collective ways in which societies imagine and regulate eroticism (A. Hunt 1999). Books, even those deemed obscene, document the desires, anxieties, and moral boundaries of their time. However, since the OPI meeting and any attempt to define erotica had never reached a definitive conclusion, we can only understand such imagination by examining how the issue was raised. The intense debate on obscene publications may also be understood as a consequence of advancements in publishing and distribution, which expanded access to a diverse reading repertoire and reshaped the literary landscape.

4 *Tjabul* in Higher Definition: Film, Photography, and Printing

The post-Second World War era was marked by rapid technological advancement. As physical combat ceased, global competition shifted to the manufacture of trailblazing machines, such as the satellites and spacecraft that sent the first men into space, nuclear weapons, and other military equipment, as well as computers and cybernetics. Nations with access to capital and research capabilities exported technological developments and shipped this power to other parts of the world, reshaping cultural and political dynamics. Entertainment, too, became part of this global exchange, circulating in increasingly diverse forms. Consequently, in some parts of the world, such as Indonesia, folk arts were forced to compete with these imported cultural products due to their importance to strengthening diplomatic ties.

Film emerged as one of the most influential media in the early independence period. Usmar Ismail's political masterpiece, *Darah dan doa* (*The long march*, 1950) evoked a nationalist spirit and marked the beginning of a national cinematic identity. The first day of the shooting, 30 March 1950, is now com-

memorated as the National Film Day. Despite their patriotic intentions, national films in the 1950s were largely inspired by Western cinema, both aesthetically and commercially. Usmar, for example, drew inspiration from Italian *neorealismo*, using on-location shoots instead of a studio set to catch the natural light and enhance his works' realism. His films featured large casts and addressed working-class narratives, using social commentary to foster a sense of unity and national belonging (Hanan 2017).

Still, Indonesian cinema faced stiff competition from foreign films. While around 35 films were produced annually in *bahasa Indonesia*, the number of imported films far exceeded this. In 1950 alone, 54 local features were released compared to 863 imported films, with 660 of the latter coming from the United States (Hanan 2017:69). Such competition shaped audience preferences and classified cinema-going experiences. First-class cinemas in Central Jakarta, such as Astoria, Globe, and Metropole, catered to the Hollywood-loving, young audience, while second-class venues like Grand, Rex, or Rivoli screened Bollywood films, attracting working-class audiences. Award-winning films were screened in Podium, where STICUSA⁹-sponsored films and music performances were facilitated, giving high status to the cinema. Misbach Yusa Biran, a renowned filmmaker, recalled his teenage years frequenting elite cinemas and observing this cultural divide (Biran 2008).

Hollywood's influence extended beyond film aesthetics to the realm of celebrity culture. American film stars became new idols, featured in magazines, and inspired local aspiring artists. Stardom played a crucial role in determining the success of a film, and the allure of foreign actors helped fuel the growth of Indonesia's own film industry. Film studios were established, and the need for a new artistic workforce attracted young people to careers in this industry, both behind and in front of the camera.¹⁰

Entertainment magazines, such as *Selecta*, *Varia*, or *Aneka*, dedicated extensive coverage to international movie stars, showcasing glamorous close-ups and the latest fashion trends. These glossy images helped shape a new

9 Stichting voor Culturele Samenwerking (STICUSA) was a Dutch colonial cultural cooperation board, established in 1948 to facilitate cooperation between the Netherlands and the former colonies, including Indonesia. For more detailed information about the activities in Indonesia, see Dolk 2012.

10 One example was Biran, who dropped out of high school to work for Perfini, before going on to become a famous director. Unlike the jobs available in the industry today, the jobs available in the early days were far from glamorous. This did not, however, stop the workers from working as hard as possible, given the reputation of Perfini. For a more detailed description of what life was like working for Perfini, including the on-site working environment, see Biran 2008.

urban lifestyle, more oriented towards Western modes of dress, music, and leisure. The intersection of print media and films supported the growth of popular culture, intensifying anxieties about the moral implications of Western influence, particularly among conservative and nationalist circles.

As a sophisticated medium of art, cinema amplified every element on screen, including obscenity. Technicolour technology, which exploited the three primary colours, produced vibrant images that monochromatic ones could not match. On large screens, actors looked more enchanting, their beauty magnified and their sensuality heightened. In addition, promotional stills displayed in theatres to attract potential audiences further enhanced this effect, offering realistic, zoomed-in visuals that surpassed hand-drawn sketches.

These technological innovations made foreign films especially appealing to younger audiences, who associated visual sophistication with modernity. The adoption of advanced film techniques signalled cultural progress and social aspiration. In this context, visual technology did not stand alone; instead, it was supported by the press and photography, forming a media ecosystem that shaped public desire and moral discourse.

Before technicolour films and glossy magazines captivated urban audiences, photography had already established a visual language of desire and domination in the Dutch East Indies. In colonial times, European travelling photographers took pictures of the people in the colony for a range of purposes, including ethnographic documentation, commercial exploitation, and the satisfaction of erotic fascination. Young native women, often sex workers, were photographed nude for White Western eyes, preserving their bodies as sexualized objects for foreign consumption (Museum voor Volkenkunde 1989).¹¹ These images circulated widely in the form of postcards, a genre that gained immense popularity in the early-twentieth-century European art scenes. Supported by advances in photo reproduction technology, erotic and pornographic postcards became mass-produced commodities, propelled by the twin engines of capitalism and colonialism (Prochaska 2001).

Such postcards did more than titillate; they also encoded fantasies of racial and gendered domination. Female bodies were treated as commodities, artistic objects, Orientalist spectacles, and moral indicators (Klich 2001). This genre specifically reached its prime towards the end of the first decade of the twentieth century, but its legacy endured. As printing technologies evolved, nude

11 For a more detailed historical account of photography in the Dutch East Indies, including examples of erotic photography, see Museum voor Volkenkunde 1989.

pictures were no longer confined to postcards. Film negatives could be reproduced and sold as standalone photographs, increasingly detached from artistic framing and marketed for explicit consumption. In this shift, nude crossed a threshold from art to obscenity as its circulation multiplied and its exclusivity diminished. Unlike artistic works, which were often restricted to collectors or patrons, pornographic images became widely accessible, transforming private desire into public anxiety.

The controversy surrounding the erotic photographs of Nurnaningsih illustrated the tensions between artistic expression, the modern American dream, and cultural conservatism in post-independence Indonesia. Her response to the case and her Hollywood goal can be interpreted within a narrative of liberation and cosmopolitan ambition. The use of technology in photography and printing not only magnified the eroticism but had also allegedly transported it from black-market exchanges to foreign producers. The case gained a lot of negative reactions from the national film scene, which framed it as moral crisis. The authorities, including the police and the attorney general's office, ordered an investigation into it. Renowned filmmaker Djamaluddin Malik deplored the act, saying that nude photography was still unacceptable for Indonesia's predominantly Muslim society. Bakaruddin, a Malay film producer, also responded similarly, saying that the Indonesian film scene had lost its 'Eastern modesty' and become too modern. He stated with certainty that it was impossible that Malay actors would do the same (Djambak n.y.).

The Malay film industry in the 1950s, which was closely connected to Indonesia's, also navigated similar tensions between modernity and tradition. While decolonization encouraged expressions of national progress, it also resulted in an ambivalent portrayal of the ideal modern Malay woman, a figure who was neither temptress nor mother. One Malay actor, Maria Menado, faced a backlash in 1956 for dressing in immodest Western clothing, which she defended as her own interpretation of the 'modern way'. Modernity in postcolonial Malay, usually represented by the female models in magazines and the entertainment industry, suggested that the modern national woman should remain tethered to her domestic role (Barnard 2018).

Such similarities between the Indonesian and the Malay film industries reflected the shared notion of an ideal modern woman. Nurnaningsih herself had an unconventional lifestyle, living alone in a rented garage, painting, practising yoga, marrying multiple times, and leaving her child in familial care to pursue her acting career (Djambak n.y.). Her bohemian existence stood in stark contrast to that of the ideal woman, embodying a defiant reimagination of womanhood in the postcolonial landscape. The controversies surrounding Nurnaningsih and Maria Menado illuminate how modernity, especially when

embodied by women, was both desired and feared, revealing the fragile balance between national progress and cultural preservation in the wake of decolonization.

Photography is a powerful tool to produce and preserve obscenity, particularly as technological advancements enabled mass duplication and distribution. The development of negatives and affordable printing methods allowed images to circulate widely. Fandoms flourished through entertainment magazines, such as *Varia*, where readers exchanged photos of, and merchandise relating to, their idols. Colour photography also intensified this dynamic, enhancing the stars' sexual appeal and transforming them into consumable objects of desire.

Before the more realistic images brought about by photography, printing technology had made sexual fantasy more accessible. In eighteenth-century Europe, erotic literature was developed from collections of aristocratic portraiture as a way to dismantle the aristocracy. During the French Revolution, print publications played an important role in producing political pamphlets, newspapers, and books to spread revolutionary ideas and mobilize the masses. Pornography was weaponized to delegitimize the monarchy, through pamphlets and books depicting Marie Antoinette and other members of the royal family in demeaning poses. Such materials aimed to be disrespectful and to delegitimize and challenge the traditional hierarchies and norms (L. Hunt 2013). As the genre of the novel gained popularity, erotica reached broader audiences, making novels even more popular and readers sexually aroused.

In post-war Indonesia, rising literacy and expanding access to print media created the space for similar transformations. The publishing industry developed as printing technologies became more affordable and sophisticated, breaking the monopoly previously held by the Dutch- and Chinese-owned presses. Mass media continued to be issued in *bahasa Indonesia*, with subscriptions rising and readers personalizing their interests. In the 1950s, periodicals served not only as political tools but also as cultural platforms. *Star Weekly* magazine, for example, reported on the latest national and international political issues combined with celebrity gossip, domestic tips, and supplements for children and teenagers. More targeted publications, such as *Wanita* (Women), focused on empowering women both in their domestic and public roles. Newspapers either became the supporters (*Harian Rakjat* [The people's daily]) or critics (*Indonesia Raja* [Great Indonesia]) of the government.

The growth in Indonesian mass media also facilitated periodicals that catered to entertainment purposes, often featuring show business coverage or fiction. These publications occupied a transitional space between popular appeal and moral scrutiny and put them in the 'obscene' category. Reports

about the confiscation of books and magazines labelled as *batjaan tjabul* indicated the growing unrest about obscenity in society. In 1953, the Serikat Perusahaan Surat kabar (SPS, Newspaper Companies Union) established the Panitia Susila Pers (Committee of Press Morality) as an outcome of the SPS's Eighth Congress in Medan. The committee included politicians A.K. Lubis, Asa Bafagih, and Siauw Giok Tjhan, who were tasked with formulating guidelines to regulate obscenity in magazine and newspaper advertisements (Rachim 1977:67). As reported in the media, the authorities confiscated more than fifty titles, such as *Bikini*, *Genit* (Flirty), *Berahi* (Lust), and *Monalisa* in the 1950s (Rachim 1977). As indicated in relation to the concern about obscene literature in literary circles, it was difficult to stop its dissemination, as technology facilitated faster and cheaper production. It also meant that, where previously ownership of obscene materials had been limited to aristocratic circles, this was no longer the case, and the exclusivity of ownership was lost. The regular circulation of lewd materials triggered disquiet about the future of the nation, as young people immersed themselves in these corrupted arts.

5 Building a Nation on the Moral High Ground: Social Commentary and Morality Assessment

A reader's letter to *Star Weekly* magazine signed by Miss Tan Giok Lan and Miss E. Tan Giok Hua complained about two photographs printed in the previous issue of the magazine on page 8.¹² One image featured Italian movie star Gina Lollobrigida receiving a hand-kiss from Chicago's theatre mogul, Emil Margiotta; in another, she kissed his forehead in return. This form of respect was labelled in the caption as the 'continental style'. The readers perceived the pictures as depicting '*onzedelijkheid*' (immorality), which to them seemed ironic because, in the same issue, *Star Weekly* had responded to another reader's concern about the dangers of American comic books. On the circulation of comic books, the magazine had replied to this letter in a two-page article about the case of a child who had committed suicide, having imitated a scene in a comic strip. The magazine had agreed with the reader that parents should actively demand censorship as children could copy drawings in comic strips, particularly those containing vivid images of violence and sex.¹³ As a response to the two women's concern, *Star Weekly* wrote,

12 'Menjinggung perasaan kesusilaan', *Star Weekly*, 2-10-1954.

13 'Anak ketjil bunuh diri: Atas petunjuk tjerita bergambar (comic strips)', *Star Weekly*, 2-10-1954.

Such a kiss is completely free from sexual motives, because its intention is reverence. [...] What, then, could have offended you? Maybe the strapless dress of the woman we published in the picture on page 8. If so, we understand the meaning of the two female readers above. And we will no longer publish such photos in *Star Weekly*.¹⁴

The letter may seem like a regular complaint from a reader, but it gives us an idea of the various definitions of *tjabul*. A woman's body was regulated through the expectations placed on her regarding her behaviour and appearance. Even though both the readers and the editor had different perceptions of the same picture, they agreed that there was something inappropriate about it.

In the case of Lollobrigida, the depiction of her body was compared to the moral panic surrounding crime and violence in comic books. On the same page as the letter criticizing her photographs, *Star Weekly* published two additional responses from readers named Khouw Soen Hok and Ho K. Liang, who expressed support for the magazine's position on American comic strips. Unlike the letter about Lollobrigida, these responses focused less on sexuality and were more concerned about the perceived psychological impact of graphic content, citing vampire stories as an example, on children. Khouw also praised *Star Weekly* for bringing up the issue and concluded by recommending a committee to censor graphic books.¹⁵ Ho, while also endorsing the article, specifically mentioned *Kiam Hiap*, the first Indonesian martial-arts comic, the depictions of violence and sexual harassment in which could pose risks to young readers.¹⁶

Being on the same page and relating to the same issue of the magazine, these three letters, despite having individual concerns on morality, indicate the way the authors thought that *tjabul*, whether sexual or violent, might compromise the future of the youth and thus the future of the nation. The anti-Western sentiment in the letters showed that *tjabul* products were not only sexual but also violent. The tone used in each of the letters was also assertive, using a particular instance to address a general issue. The editorial response to Lollobrigida's pho-

14 'Tjiunan demikian bebas sama sekali dari motif2 sexueel, karena maksudnja ialah menghormat. [...] Kalau begitu apa jang telah bisa menjinggung perasaan pematja? Mungkin pakaian strapless dari wanita jang kami muat gambarnya dihalaman 8 itu. Djika begitu, kami mengerti maksud kedua pematja wanita diatas. Dan foto demikian tidak akan kami muat lagi di Star Weekly'. ('Menjinggung perasaan kesusilaan', *Star Weekly*, 2-10-1954.)

15 'Anak2 dan comic strips', *Star Weekly*, 9-10-1954.

16 'Dua matjam cerita Kiam Hiap', *Star Weekly*, 9-10-1954.

tos also illustrates *Star Weekly's* sentiment on morality and modernity: Western influences were inevitable but should not be exempted from criticism.

Star Weekly was a prominent magazine produced for those of *peranakan* (Chinese or Chinese Indonesian) descent, first published in 1946. By 1950, under the leadership of Auwjong Peng Koen—later known as P.K. Ojong, founder of *Kompas*, Indonesia's largest newspaper—the magazine had become a platform for articulating a hybrid Chinese Indonesian identity. Among its efforts were its frequent critiques of the Indonesian government's further alignment with China and communism. With a diverse adult readership across the genders, *Star Weekly* covered a wide range of topics, including national and international politics. The magazine stopped circulating in 1961, as the government banned it for being increasingly critical of the government in its later editions (Lev 1991). Its agony aunt page was an interesting read, offering insights into everyday romance and relationships, such as arranged marriages and etiquette within Chinese Indonesian communities. The column documents how the Chinese Indonesian identity was negotiated through everyday experiences and social expectations.

Reflecting a popular trend in mid-century magazines, *Star Weekly's* agony aunt page encouraged readers to discuss personal and social issues. The column was written by two female characters, Nj. Oei and Nj. Seng (Mrs Oei and Mrs Seng), who responded to questions with their own distinct stylistic and ideological approaches. Subjects ranged from questions about how to cope with emotional distress or how to choose a marriage partner to expressing concern about current societal issues. Nj. Oei's responses tended to be more conservative; she criticized Western influence in fashion, such as the high slit in the cheongsam ('*split dress tjang ie terlalu tinggi*'), and leisure activities, warning that young people should not be alone at the theatre ('*muda-mudi djanjan berduaan di bioskop*'). In one letter, she attributed the growing immorality to the aftermath of the Revolutionary War, suggesting that women had become bold enough to seduce married men in public spaces such as swimming pools.

Nj. Seng, on the other hand, adopted a more considerate and balanced tone. Eventually gaining her own column, named 'Ruangan Nj. Seng' (Mrs. Seng's room), she often considered different perspectives before offering advice. For example, responding to a reader who had asked about ballroom dancing, she rejected the notion that it was 'demoralizing and scandalous' (*merusakkan moral dan melanggar kesopanan*), but acknowledged the potential risks of unmarried people being in the same room and dancing. She proposed the need for alternative forms of social engagement. Towards the end of the 1950s, Nj. Seng had become the dominant voice in the advice columns, reflecting the

magazine's evolving liberal stance in response to changing cultural and political currents.

Besides the structured format of advice columns, magazines also provided space for more spontaneous and personal expressions of concern. On several occasions, magazines published a full-length open letter submitted to the editorial team but addressed to a particular person, usually a friend or family member. These letters invited broader readership of intimate exchanges from which others might learn. In one issue of *Wanita*¹⁷ magazine, a letter from a woman named Rita to her best friend Liza was published. The letter mainly contains Rita's deep concern about the society she felt 'had lost direction and leadership', attributing the decline to the influence of American films featuring cowboys and sexual scenes. She linked such obscenity to a rise in sexual offences and other crimes, and voiced her dissatisfaction with the government's failure to intervene in the distribution of imported films. Her letter concluded with a passionate call to action: '[I] call out and propose everywhere, in communities, in newspapers, in magazines so that the import of obscene films that contain immorality can be stopped and those that have been screened be withdrawn from circulation.'¹⁸

What makes this letter particularly intriguing is that it appeared as a magazine article, introduced by a man named D. Makstojo. In his 'confession', Makstojo recounts how the letter was 'accidentally' discovered by his dog while it rummaged through a pile of garbage, a fictionalized setup that casts him as both narrator and protagonist. He vividly describes the condition of the lost letter and its unexpected recovery, adopting a literary tone that blurs the boundaries between reportage and storytelling. Based on the style, Makstojo concludes that the letter must have been written by a woman, because men lacked the sensibility to write such a 'beautiful and polished letter'. Using a letter from a

17 *Wanita* was first published in 1949. In his memoirs, Ajip Rosidi told a story about his meeting with Armijn Pane in 1954, whom he mentioned as being the editor-in-chief of *Wanita* and whose house in Jalan Cemara No. 10 was used as the magazine's editorial office (Rosidi 2008). Due to his involvement with Balai Pustaka, where he managed the publication of the magazines, Pane served as an advisor for *Wanita*. It was, however, Pane's wife, Pudjiati Yong Brot, known as Nj. Armijn Pane, who was in charge of the magazine, along with Sihwati Nawangulan, the wife of the minister of foreign affairs, Ruslan Abdulgani. In later editions, Pudjiati's name was written as Nj. Pudjiati, while Sihwati's remained Nj. Ruslan Abdulgani. Among the editorial team members were the Said sisters, Lies and Tity, who were at the beginning of their career.

18 '... serukan dan andjurkan dimana-mana, dikumpulan-kumpulan, disurat-kabarz, dimadjallah-madjallah supaya impor film2 tjabal jang tak bermoral dihentikan dan film2 jang sudah beredar ditjabut dari peredarannja' (Makstojo 1958:519).

woman can be understood as an attempt to invite women's participation in combating this moral problem. By amplifying a 'beautiful and polished' voice, instead of a fierce one, the article appears to target middle-class women, the main readers of *Wanita*.

Makstojo closes his commentary by acknowledging that Rita's opinion had made some sense to him, as he liked Hollywood films himself. He agrees that Western films had contributed to a moral crisis, including the rise of the *crossboy*¹⁹ phenomenon. Rita's letter is thus positioned as a moment of moral awakening that calls for collective action. In his final remark, Makstojo wished that Rita's voice would echo and inspire women—referred to as '*kaummu*' (your people)—to join the effort in restoring moral order. The narrative framing in this letter reinforces gendered notions of moral authority and illustrates how the media strategically employed sentimental women voices to generate virtue and regulate cultural consumption in a modernizing society.

While sentimental narratives such as Rita's letter were used to mobilize moral discourse, *Wanita* magazine also played an empowering role. It is important to note that most of the articles featured in *Wanita* were dedicated to women's empowerment. In general, the magazine embodied the figure of modern urban women, someone capable of balancing their domestic responsibilities with public participation. *Wanita* gave voice to the spirit of Kartini's critique of genderized injustice and her vision of emancipation. As Grace V.S. Chin observes, the adoption of Kartini's ideas in women's organizations in the 1950s showed a deep ambivalence, as manifested in the contrasting ideals of Gerwani and the Persatuan Wanita Republik Indonesia (Perwari, Women's Federation of the Indonesian Republic). Gerwani fought for equality for all women from all classes, emphasizing collective struggle and class-inclusive equality. Meanwhile, Perwari focused on individual empowerment, often reflecting middle-class aspirations and personal development (Chin 2020).

The editorial team behind *Wanita* consisted largely of intellectual women, many of whom were married to prominent figures in Indonesian politics. Their work often appropriated Kartini's vision of modern Indonesian women who were educated, socially engaged, and committed to reform. The magazine regularly addressed issues such as marriage law and education and often featured stories about women from other countries, reflecting their cosmopolitan

19 '*Cross boy*' (also '*cross girl*') is an old Indonesian slang term that refers to the type of young people/teenagers who spend their time hanging out in the streets. They are usually depicted as causing trouble and disturbing order. Popular Indonesian writer Motinggo Busje had written *Cross mama* in 1968, which depicted the life of middle-class urbanites whose problems were derived from a lack of morals.

outlook. By the late 1950s, articles about national and international politics became more frequent, showing their expanding vision beyond their domestic realm. At the same time, they also maintained their domestic position, for example by using their husband's name as their chosen form of address. Catering primarily to a readership of middle-class, educated women, *Wanita* promoted a vision of modern liberal womanhood, embracing civic participation while navigating entrenched gender expectations.

In this context, the publication of Rita's letter through a male intermediary may seem contradictory. However, considering the complexities of Indonesian women's empowerment in the 1950s, where the separation of their public and domestic roles was still non-negotiable, such contradictions could be expected. Whether or not the letter's authenticity can be verified, its concern over obscenity was again affected by the uncertainty of a nation in transition—a nation that was unpredictable, constantly changing, and gullible. Encouraging the government to take measures to police these obscene materials, at the same time indicates that people had found a channel to express their opinions, something that was impossible in pre-independence Indonesia. The rise of liberal democracy, increased literacy, and technological advancements all contributed to the thriving public participation in the national mission of finding cultural and moral direction.

Building on the role of the media as a channel for civic discourse, the readers' page also indicates how mass publications had been used not only to accommodate the *vox populi* but also to amplify political ideologies. On the leftist side, *Harian Rakjat* was a prime example of a communist publication used to channel left-wing politics. Since its first issue, in 1951, the Partai Komunis Indonesia (PKI, Indonesian Communist Party) had used the daily newspaper as a strategic tool, particularly during the first legislative elections in 1955. The paper not only promoted the PKI's platform of decolonizing arts and culture but also foregrounded moral reform as a key electoral issue.

Speaking in front of high-school students and teachers at Radjekwesi Theatre in Bodjonegoro on 29 December 1954, the PKI's leading figure, Njoto, endorsed the upcoming Kongres Demoralisasi Peladjar (Student Congress on Immoralities) and condemned the circulation of *batjaan tjabul* and other obscene materials as a threat to youth morality.²⁰ As both a representative of the PKI and editor of *Harian Rakjat*, Njoto's visit to Bodjonegoro reflected the party's broader campaign to align political mobilization and cultural puri-

20 'Njoto di Bodjonegoro: P.K.I. menuntut pelarangan segala jang tjabul', *Harian Rakjat*, 5-1-1955.

fication. In addition, *Harian Rakjat* consistently called for boycotts and censorship of imperialist arts and culture, urging structural change to combat moral decay.²¹ Efforts included targeting *batjaan tjabul*²² and policing certain types of attire, such as the *you-can-see* (sleeveless dresses or tops), which student groups in Yogyakarta protested about in 1955 as being symbols of indecency.²³

Under the leadership of Njoto and Mula Naibaho, *Harian Rakjat's* cultural pages became a crucible for the 'communist imagination' in which they featured contributions from leftist artists and writers who rejected Western influence. As Joebaar Ajoeb warned, imported literature, films, and music were 'killing patriotism' (*mematikan patriotisme*) and 'reviving individualism' (*menghidupkan individualisme*). Tracing the cultural pages of *Harian Rakjat* during the 1950s, Stephen Miller (2015) notes that *tjabul* was often associated with Western, particularly American culture, with pulp literature and Hollywood films attacked for promoting shallow, individual freedom. This was seen in cowboy films, detective stories, and provocative scenes in novels and magazines and was deemed unproductive to the communist ideal. In this ideological framing, moral reform was inseparable from national liberation, and turning away from the West became a moral imperative (Miller 2015).

Gerwani's condemnation of Western, imperialist decadence was particularly assertive. Unlike other women's organizations, as Saskia E. Wieringa (2002) notes, Gerwani explicitly linked moral corruption to fascism and imperialism. They identified American popular culture products, such as rock 'n' roll, films, and dances, as obstacles to women's progress. Their critique was expressed not only through ideologically affiliated media, such as *Harian Rakjat* and *Api Kartini*, but also through direct action, including calls to ban films like *Rock around the clock*, *Don't knock the rock*, and *The desert fox*. These efforts received support from their local leftist allies, such as Lekra and Pemuda Rakyat (The People's Youth), and internationally by the Women's International Democratic Federation (Wieringa 2002). Drawing inspiration from Kartini and Clara Zetkin, Gerwani envisaged women's liberation from injustice in the workforce and marriage. Throughout their active years, Gerwani members were at the forefront of national politics and maintained international ties.

This ideological stance extended beyond cultural critique into legal advocacy, particularly around marriage law, a key issue in Gerwani's struggle. The organization promoted equal rights for women and children, viewing legal

21 'Masaalah demoralisasi', *Harian Rakjat*, 24-2-1955.

22 'Penerbitz lektur tjabul mulai diperkara', *Harian Rakjat*, 22-1-1955.

23 'Anti gaun "you can see"', *Harian Rakjat*, 5-1-1955.

reform as essential to dismantling unjust structures. Gerwani's prominent leader, Umi Sardjono, asserted that in order to achieve a better society, all kinds of imperialism should be abolished (McGregor and Rahayu 2023). Gerwani's vision of a 'healthy revolutionary' world was based on collective 'healthy love', opposing the obscenity they saw in imperialist cultures as perpetuating immorality. Yet, despite its progressive stance on women's rights, Gerwani maintained heterosexual relationships as the ideal and only form of love. Its members were rarely engaged in discussions about sexual liberation and, as in other socialist nations, Gerwani upheld other forms of sexuality outside 'socialist monogamy' as divergent (Wieringa 2002:248–9). The organization's critique of sexuality, prostitution, and obscenity stemmed from a broader rejection of Western degeneracy. Still, Gerwani's core endeavour remained fighting imperialism. Its acceptance of French movie star Brigitte Bardot, despite her sexualized image, was rooted in her anti-war attitude, showing that Gerwani was, first and foremost, about dismantling imperialism.

Across the diverse variety of mass media in Indonesia in the 1950s, it becomes evident that periodicals were more than a source of information; they were also ideological tools that mediated public sentiment and moral discourse. Publications such as *Harian Rakjat*, *Star Weekly*, and *Wanita* each engaged with the issue of obscenity through a different ideological lens, indicating the broader postcolonial anxieties about modernity, national identity, and cultural sovereignty. In the spirit of fighting against Western imperialism, *Harian Rakjat* depicted obscenity as a symptom of Western moral decay, particularly American liberalism, which threatened to destabilize revolutionary values. The newspaper's campaign to eradicate *tjabul* was framed as a moral imperative, fearing that unchecked desire would undermine national progress.

Meanwhile, *Star Weekly* approached the problem differently, almost always through a more liberal and individualistic framework. It relied on offering advice, including encouraging parental guidance and personal responsibility in navigating the dangers of *prikkellectuur*, or titillating reading materials, and erotic imagery. The tone was less militant and more pedagogical, suggesting that morality was a matter of individual choice rather than structural reform.²⁴ *Wanita*, on the other hand, focused on educating women about their double duty. Its articles and advice column were more concerned with appropriateness, etiquette, hygiene, and family values, which were often drawn from West-

24 'Pengaruh buku batjaan: Harus waspada terhadap buku tjabul jang selimut', *Star Weekly*, 10-10-1953.

ern standards of propriety. While less overtly political, *Wanita's* engagement with obscenity reveals a moderate negotiation with regard to modern femininity.

The discourse surrounding *tjabul* in 1950s Indonesian media reveals more than a moral panic. It also exposes a deeper negotiation of identity, power, and emotional governance. Through the lens of *tjabul*, we see how pleasure and transgression became focal points for ideological debates, whether framed as threats to revolutionary ideals, challenges to liberal autonomy, or concerns within domestic pedagogy. Media outlets reflected public sentiment towards morality and actively shaped the sentiment by channelling emotions, such as fear, shame, and pride, to characterize moral boundaries and national aspirations. As Ahmed's concept of the politics of emotions suggests, these feelings were not private; they were public instruments for building a sense of belonging and exclusion in a postcolonial context.

6 Conclusion

In most discussions about obscenity and morality, feelings (*perasaan*) of morality (*susila*) were presumed to be *terlanggar* (violated) or *tersinggung* (offended). Obscenity, then, was not merely a visual or textual excess but also a problem of emotions that involved the political economy of media and the moral architecture of the nation. It operated by establishing an 'other', whose presence threatened the normative order. As Ahmed argues, responding to the obscenity presumes affective returns that also attributed 'others [with] meaning and value in the very act of apparent separation' (Ahmed 2004:28). This emotional logic led to the policing of bodies, both physical and artistic, through judgements about what should and, more importantly, what should not be done. These feelings materialized in various forms, from genuine concerns about the future of the children and the nation to gatekeeping cultural boundaries. The young generation symbolizes national hope, and safeguarding them from perceived moral threats became a collective imperative. To define *tjabul* was to confront divergence in a dynamic yet vulnerable society, one where outcomes were never fixed but always negotiated.

As women entered the public sphere, their visibility in different degrees became the target of moral assessment. The multitude of positions on this issue deserves its own explanation. Obscenity and immorality were genderized terrains, where women bore disproportionate judgement and punishment. The 1950s marked a flourishing of women's movements, demanding better treatment and a more equal, gender-based labour division. This phenomenon dis-

rupted social norms and was reflected in artistic and intellectual circles, where figures such as Pramoedya and Alisjahbana mentioned women's progress as part of the problem with obscenity. Women's magazines responded critically to these tensions, voicing distress over obscene materials while also becoming targets of demonization during public scandals. In the case of the scandal concerning the nude photographs of Nurnaningsih, women's bodies and minds were the sources of immorality. Her nude images became objects with dual functions: traded and circulated as commodities while also being condemned as representative of moral decline. Her agency in navigating the liberal economy was met with a familial and ideological backlash, revealing the layered politics of female embodiment.

Similar anxieties were echoed in the voices of the two female readers of *Star Weekly*, who criticized a global superstar's gesture, and Nurnaningsih's Gerwani sister, who believed there was something indecent about a woman being provocative. Their critiques reflected a belief that foreign values, especially those embodied by women, should not be imitated and displayed in public. Women's opinions were often mediated through male agency, encouraged in intellectual meetings, or facilitated through editorial framing. Women were both producers and objects of knowledge about *tjabul*, caught in a web of visibility, regulation, and representation.

Finally, the formation of sexual knowledge in 1950s Indonesia was inseparable from power relations. No single political power was authoritative enough to determine the boundaries of obscenity. The reliance on colonial legal remnants to police morality stood in tension with the spirit of postcolonial freedom, as the West was cast as the moral antagonist. The discourse on *tjabul* thus reveals a nation in transition: negotiating modernity, morality, and identity through the interaction of emotion, ideology, and gender.

Acknowledgements

This article was written with financial support from the Lembaga Pengelola Dana Pendidikan (LPDP, Indonesian Endowment Fund for Education Agency).

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